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Torch infeksiyasi va uning homilaga ta'siri

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada TORCH infeksiyasi, uni qo'zg'atuvchilari haqida ma'lumotlar mavjud. Bu kasallik azaldan ko'pgina davlatlar orasida havfli kasalliklar sirasiga kirib kelmoqda. TORCH bu bir qancha infeksiyalarning jamlanmasi hisoblanadi. Bu qo'zg'atuvchilar qatoriga CMV hamda cCMV, gepatit, Oitv, gerpez viruslari kiradi. Har yili ko'plab chaqaloqlar hamda onalar TORCH infeksiyasidan aziyat chekishadi. Ushbu maqolada aynan dastlab infeksiyadan qanday himoyalanish, uni diagnostika qilish haqida so'z yuritiladi. Bu kasallik ayol organizmida uzoq vaqtgacha belgisiz rivojlanishi mumkin. Agarda ayol homilador bo'lsa kasallik o'zini namoyon etishni boshlaydi. Bola organizmida esa og'ir asoratlarni keltirib chiqaradi. Shuning uchun har bir ayol homiladorlikdan oldin TORCH uchun analiz topshirishi shart. Bu analizlar qatoriga PCR, qon tahlili, virusli tekshiruv shuningdek qo'shimcha tekshiruv sifatida KT hamda MRTni keltirish mumkin. Bu infeksiyaning og'ir asoratlari sirasiga homilaning tushishi, vaqtdan oldin bolaning tug'ilishini va qayta homilador bo'la olmaslikni ham kiritish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: TORCH, Sifilis, gerpes, OITS, ZIKA, Toksoplazma gondi, sitomegalovirus (CMV), cCMV, qon tahlili, KT, MRT, IgM, IgG, seroprevalans, Elishay test, PCR, IUFD, plasenta, homila.

Торч-инфекция и ее влияние на плод

Гулумжонова Зиёдахон Гафуржон кызы

Андижанский филиал Kokand University

Аннотация: данной статье приведены сведения о TORCH-инфекции и ее возбудителях. Это заболевание издавна входит в число опасных среди многих стран. TORCH представляет собой совокупность нескольких инфекций. К числу этих возбудителей относятся вирусы CMV и cCMV, гепатит, ВИЧ, герпес. Ежегодно многие новорожденные и матери страдают от TORCH-инфекции. В этой статье рассматривается, как изначально защититься от инфекции и как ее диагностировать. Заболевание может длительное время бессимптомно развиваться в женском организме. Если женщина беременна, болезнь начинает проявляться. В организме ребенка она вызывает тяжелые осложнения. Поэтому каждая женщина перед беременностью должна пройти обследование на TORCH. К числу этих анализов можно отнести ПЦР, анализ крови, вирусологическое исследование, а также KT и MPT в качестве дополнительных обследований. К числу тяжелых осложнений этой инфекции относится поражение плода.

Ключевые слова. TORCH, Сифилис, герпес, СПИД, ЗИКА, Тохопlasma gondii, цитомегаловирус (ЦМВ), ЦМВИ, анализ крови, KT, MPT, IgM, IgG, серопревалентность, ИФА-тест, ПЦР, ВИФД, плацента, плод.

Torch infection and its effect on the fetus

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Annotatsion: This article provides information about TORCH infection and its pathogens. This disease has long been considered dangerous in many countries. TORCH is a combination of several infections. These pathogens include CMV and cCMV viruses, hepatitis, HIV, and herpes. Every year, many newborns and mothers suffer from TORCH infection. This article discusses how to initially protect yourself from the infection and how to diagnose it. The disease can develop asymptotically in a woman's body for a long time. If a woman is pregnant, the disease begins to manifest itself. In the child's body, it causes severe complications. Therefore, every woman should undergo a TORCH examination before pregnancy. These tests include PCR, blood tests, virological tests, as well as CT and MRI as additional examinations. Severe complications of this infection include fetal damage.

Key words: TORCH, Syphilis, herpes, AIDS, ZIKA, Toxoplasma gondii, cytomegalovirus (CMV), cCMV, blood test, CT, MRI, IgM, IgG, seroprevalence, ELISA test, PCR, IUFD, placenta, fetus

Kirish. STORCH (ingliz tilida TORCHES yoki TORCH)- ginekologiya sohasida qoëllaniladigan tushuncha. TORCH infeksiyasi - bu mikroorganizmlarning muhim guruhlaridan iborat boëlib, ular belgilersiz, asemptomatik va homiladorlik davrida aniqlash qiyin, ammo tugëma anomaliyalar, oligogidramniozlar, FGR (homila oëshini cheklash) shaklida paydo boëlishi mumkin. Bu infeksiya IUFD (intrauterin homila oëlimi), qayta homilador boëla olmaslik (RPL) va oëlik tugëilishga olib keladi. TORCH qisqartmasi immunolog Andre Nahmias tomonidan yaratilgan [7]. STORCH qisqartmasi: S= Sifilis (patogen pallidum Treponema), T = Toksoplazmoz (patogen Toksoplazma gondii), O = boshqa masalan; Parvovirus B19 (patogen qizilcha virusi), Varicella-zoster virusi (suvchechak va shingillalarning qoëzgëatuvchisi), Gepatit B virusi (gepatit B qoëzgëatuvchisi), Gepatit C virusi (gepatit C qoëzgëatuvchisi), OIV (OITS patogeni), Xlamidiya (patagen xlamidiya), Coxsacke virusi, Listeria (isteriozni keltirib chiqaradigan patogen, Streptococcus agalactiae), Zika virusi [17], R = qizilcha (patogen qizilcha virusi), C = Sitomegali (patogen inson sitomegalovirusi), H = herpes simplex (patogen herpes simplex viruslari) kiradi [24]. Markaziy Amerikaning Shimoliy uchburchagida onalar oëlimi yuqori hisoblanadi [16]. Soëngi yillar holatiga koëra, El Salvador, Gvatemala va Gondurasda onalar oëlimi koeffitsienti 100 000 tirik tugëilgan chaqaloqqa mos ravishda 54, 88 ming va 129 mingni tashkil etdi [1]. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining 2030- yilgacha Barqaror rivojlanish kun tartibidagi maqsadlar onalar oëlimini kamaytirish, yangi tugëilgan chaqaloqlar va 5 yoshgacha

boʻlgan bolalar oʻrtasida oldini olish mumkin boʻlgan oʻlimni tugatish va yuqumli kasalliklar tarqalishiga qarshi kurashishga qaratilgan [25]. Tugʻma anomaliyalarning tarqalishini kamaytirish boʻyicha xalqaro sa'y-harakatlar kuchayib borayotganiga qaramay, Markaziy Amerikaning Shimoliy uchburchagi ushbu natijalarni kamaytirish uchun sogʻliqni saqlash agentligining muvofiqlashtirilgan harakatlariga kiritilmagan [3]. JSST Amerika mintaqasida 2015 yilda qizilcha virusi va tugʻma qizilcha sindromini kasallik sifatida yoʻq qildi. Markaziy Amerikada sogʻliqni saqlash bilan bogʻliq qolgan TORCH infeksiyalari vaktsinalar va homiladorlik xavfini kamaytirish uchun cheklangan profilaktik davolanishga ega emas. TORCH infeksiyalari uchun ona va neonatal skrining dasturlari mamlakatga qarab farq qiladi va ularni standartlashtirish va kam resursli sharoitlarda qoʻllash koʻplab qiyinchiliklarga olib keladi. TORCH-infeksiyalari etiologiyasi. Infeksiyaning birlamchi taʼsiri- bu immunitet tizimi ular bilan kurashishga tayyor boʻlmagan patogenlarni homila tanasiga kirishi. Infeksiyaning ikkilamchi taʼsiri kasallik paytida ishlab chiqarilgan toksinlarning faoliyatidir. TORCH infeksiyalarining muhim xususiyati past simptomatik yoki asimptomatik namoyon boʻlishi va bu vaqtda infeksiya homilaning holatiga va homiladorlik jarayoniga salbiy taʼsir koʻrsatadi. Onaning sitomegalovirus va birlamchi infeksiya bilan homilani shikastlantirish xavfi taxminan 40% ni, toksoplazmoz bilan - homiladorlikning birinchi yarmida 15-25% va ikkinchi yarmida 60-70% ni tashkil qiladi. Koʻpincha, homila qizilcha bilan kasallanadi - homiladorlikning dastlabki uch oyida infeksiyani yuqish ehtimoli deyarli 100%. Gerpes homilaga asosan tugʻruq paytida taʼsir qiladi, bu har doim yangi tugʻilgan chaqaloq uchun jiddiy oqibatlariga olib keladi. STORCH (ingliz tilida TORCHES yoki TORCH)- ginekologiya sohasida qoʻllaniladigan tushuncha. TORCH infeksiyasi - bu mikroorganizmlarning muhim guruhlaridan iborat boʻlib, ular belgilsiz, asemptomatik va homiladorlik davrida aniqlash qiyin, ammo tugʻma anomaliyalar, oligogidramniozlar, FGR (homila oʻsishini cheklash) shaklida paydo boʻlishi mumkin. Bu infeksiya IUFD (intrauterin homila oʻlimi), qayta homilador boʻla olmaslik (RPL) va oʻlik tugʻilishga olib keladi. TORCH qisqartmasi immunolog Andre Nahmias tomonidan yaratilgan [7]. STORCH qisqartmasi: S= Sifilis (patogen pallidum Treponema), T = Toksoplazmoz (patogen Toksoplazma gondii), O = boshqa masalan; Parvovirus B19 (patogen qizilcha virusi), Varicella-zoster virusi (suvchechak va shingillalarning qoʻzgʻatuvchisi), Gepatit B virusi (gepatit B qoʻzgʻatuvchisi), Gepatit C virusi (gepatit C qoʻzgʻatuvchisi), OIV (OITS patogeni), Xlamidiya (patogen xlamidiya), Coxsacke virusi, Listeria (isteriozni

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Xulosa: Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, TORCH infeksiyalari homiladorlikda ona va homila uchun jiddiy xavf tug'diradigan sifilis, toksoplazmoz, qizilcha, sitomegalovirus, herpes va boshqa infeksiyalar guruhidir. Bu infeksiyaning eng havfli xususiyati ayol organizmida homiladorlikdan keyin belgilarni namoyon qilishi bo'lib, agarda vaqtida tashxis qo'yilmasa tug'ema nuqsonlar, homila o'eshi cheklanishi, hatto homila o'elimiga olib kelishi mumkin. Bu infeksiyalar asosan asab tizimiga ta'sir etib, tug'ema kasalliklar va nogironlikka sabab bo'ladi. Diagnostika uchun serologik testlar, PCR va ultratovush qo'llaniladi. Profilaktika choralariga asosan jinsiy hayotni sog'lom yo'lga qo'yish va gigiyena qoidalariga rioya qilish kiradi. Chunki ko'plab qo'zgatuvchilar asosan jinsiy yo'llar orqali yuqadi. TORCH-infeksiyalari butun dunyo bo'ylab ona va bola salomatligiga jiddiy ziyon yetkazadigan kasalliklar qatoriga kiradi. Ko'plab mamlakatlarda TORCH infeksiyalari uchun skrining tizimi yo'lga qo'yilmaganligi onalar va chaqaloqlar salomatligini saqlash uchun qiyinchilikka sabab bo'ladi.

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